

WORD FORMATION IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11279712

Annotation

This article provides information about word structure in Uzbek and English, you can also learn about the stages of word structure, abbreviations, onomatopoeia and specific word structures in English

Key words: Word formation, steps of word formation, acronyms, onomatopoeia

Аннотация

В этой статье представлена информация о структуре слов в узбекском и английском языках, вы также можете узнать об этапах построения слова, аббревиатурах, звукоподражаниях и конкретных структурах слов в английском языке.

Ключевые слова: Словообразование, этапы словообразования, аббревиатуры, звукоподражания.

In linguistics, word formation is the creation of a new word. Word formation is sometimes contrasted with semantic change, which is a change in a

single word's meaning. The boundary between word formation and semantic change can be difficult to define: a new use of an old word can be seen as a new word derived from an old one and identical to it in form. In linguistics (particularly morphology and lexicology), word formation refers to the ways in which new words are formed on the basis of other words or morphemes. This is also known as derivational morphology.

Uzbek is an agglutinating language. That means that more than English, even more than German, it makes words and phrases by sticking (think "gluing") a bunch of meaning-units together. The derivation contributes most word formation in Uzbek.

In English even though this is one of the main ways of forming a new word. It is not so many as in Uzbek.

We can see from the examples that English and Uzbek both use suffixes more often than prefixes

*Tinchlantiruvchi

*organizational

* **Onomatopoeia**

Words created to sound like the thing that they name.

English	Japanese	Uzbek	Indonesian
Cock-a-doo	Kokekokko	qichqirmoq	Kukuruyuk
Meow	Nya	Miyovlamo q	Meong

In compounding two or more words joined together to form a new word. It is very actively used in both languages. However, both languages have their unique compounding words:

The Uzbek language have the following types of compounding:

*N+N Xo'rozoqand

*Adj+N Oqqo'rg'on

*N+N+N gultojixo'roz

*V+P1 iskabtopar

If it is V+V or N + V the word is always written separately “ahd qilmoq”, “Olib kelmoq”.

The following types of compounds exist in English:

*N+N Football

*Adj+N blackboard

*V+N breakwater

*Prep+N Underworld

*N+ADJ snow white

*Adj+Adj blue-green

*N+V browbeat

*V+Prep takeout

*** Acronyms are words derived from the initials of several words.**

* Uzbek has several acronyms. Most of them are found in specialized vocabularies

* OITV - orttirilgan immunitet tanqisligi virusi

* AQSH - Amerika Qo'shma Shtatlari

* English also has many acronyms and most of these acronyms have entered other languages as well.

* severe acute respiratory syndrome

→ SARS

* Self-contained underwater breathing apparatus

→ SCUBA

* Other examples of Acronyms:

- | | |
|----------|--|
| a) Radar | a) Radio detecting and ranging |
| b) FYI | b) For Your Information |
| c) TGIF | c) Thanks God It's Friday |
| d) a.k.a | d) also known as |
| e) Html | e) Hypertext mark-up language |
| f) www | f) World wide web |
| g) SWOT | g) Strengths, Weaknesses,
Opportunities and Threats |

Conversion is an assigning an already existing word to a new syntactic category:
Uzbek doesn't nearly use conversion but it is not zero in this language.

Qari (adj) → qarimoq(V)

Daydi (N) → daydimog (V)

Sang'i (N) → Sang'imoq (V)

In English it is very productive and it is almost exclusively applied for all parts of
speech

butter (N) → to butter the bread

permit (V) → an entry permit

empty (A) → to empty the litter-bin

Word building : Word formation in English with examples

Admire	Admiration	Employ	Employment
Admit	Admission	Examine	Examination
Appear	Appearance	Educate	Education
Assure	Assurance	Govern	Government
Announce	Announcement	Hinder	Hindrance
Attend	Attendance	Inform	Information
Break	Breakage	Inherit	Inheritance
Bury	Burial	Improve	Improvement
Carry	Carriage	Invent	Invention

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